

Synthesis and biological activities of 4-oxo thiazolidine derivatives

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Abstract : A series of 4-oxo-2-phenyl-thiazolidin-3-yl derivatives 5a-1 have been obtained by cyclisation of various Schiff's base 4 with thioglycolic acid. The Schiff's base 4 are obtained by the reaction of appropriate carbonyl compound with (4-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazolin-2-yl-sulfanyl)-acetic acid hydrazide 3. The product is characterized by spectral and analytical data. Most of the tested compounds show promising antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Keywords : 4-Thiazolidinone, antibacterial, antifungal, quinazolidinone.

Introduction

The wide variety of quinazoline-4-one derivatives possesses biological activities such as antifungal¹, anti-cancer², antiHIV³, antiinflammatory⁴, analgesic⁵, antiviral⁶, antitubercular⁷, antimicrobial⁸. 4-Thiazolidinones are also known for versatile pharmacological activities⁹⁻¹². Hence, in present study the 2nd position in the titled compound 1¹³ having oxo group is used as the targeted compound for chemical changes¹⁴ (Scheme 1). Above observations prompted us to synthesize the title compounds (1-5) as per Scheme 1 viewing their antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Condensation of 2-thioxo-3-*p*-tolyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-quinazolin-4-one 1 with ethyl chloroacetate in dry acetone gave thiocarbonic acid *o*-ethyl ester-*S*-(4-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazoline-2-yl) ester 2. The compound 2 on ammonolysis with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol yielded (4-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazoline-2-yl-sulfanyl)-acetic acid hydrazide 3. Compound 3 underwent condensation with different carbonyls to afford the 4-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazoline-2-yl-sulfanyl acetic acid arylidene hydride 4. These intermediates 4 on cyclo-addition with mercapto acetic acid yielded five membered heterocyclic derivatives *N*-(4-oxo-2-aryl-thiazolidine-3-yl)-2-(4-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazoline-2-yl-sulfanyl)-acetamide 5. All the compounds synthesized were adequately characterized by their elemental analyses and spectral (IR and NMR) data.

Biological activity : Twelve compounds from series were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity according to Bohr dilution method^{15,16}. Antibacte-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Characterisation of compound 4b-l and 5b-l

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Found (Calcd.) (%)		
						C	H	N
4b	H	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	63	250	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	64.82 (64.85)	4.51 (4.54)	12.55 (12.60)
4c	H	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	238	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	64.82 (64.85)	4.53 (4.54)	12.57 (12.60)
4d	H	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	67	257	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	64.82 (64.85)	4.52 (4.54)	12.56 (12.60)
4e	H	3-OCH ₃ -4-OHC ₆ H ₃	54	245	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	62.58 (62.60)	4.35 (4.38)	12.14 (12.17)
4f	H	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	70	220	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	60.19 (60.12)	3.71 (3.73)	15.22 (15.24)
4g	H	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	66	208	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	60.09 (60.12)	3.69 (3.73)	15.20 (15.24)
4h	H	C ₆ H ₅	72	198	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	66.63 (66.65)	4.36 (4.38)	13.49 (13.52)
4i	H	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	70	202	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	61.48 (61.53)	3.79 (3.82)	12.47 (12.48)
4j	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	69	205	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	61.49 (61.53)	3.80 (3.82)	12.44 (12.48)
4k	H	2-FC ₆ H ₄	71	206	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ FN ₄ O ₂ S	63.85 (63.88)	3.93 (3.96)	12.92 (12.96)
4l	H	4-FC ₆ H ₄	68	180	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ FN ₄ O ₂ S	63.85 (63.88)	3.94 (3.96)	12.94 (12.96)
5b	H	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	72	250	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	60.85 (60.88)	4.52 (4.54)	10.49 (10.52)
5c	H	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	59	178-179	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	60.85 (60.88)	4.51 (4.54)	10.49 (10.52)
5d	H	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	62	315	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	60.86 (60.88)	4.52 (4.54)	10.50 (10.52)
5e	H	3-OCH ₃ -4-OHC ₆ H ₃	65	103	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	59.09 (59.11)	4.38 (4.41)	10.19 (10.21)
5f	H	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	58	127	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂	57.00 (57.03)	3.84 (3.87)	12.77 (12.79)
5g	H	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	66	120	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂	57.01 (57.03)	3.38 (3.87)	12.76 (12.79)
5h	H	C ₆ H ₅	62	> 275	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	62.11 (62.13)	4.40 (4.41)	11.13 (11.15)
5i	H	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	59	265	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	58.13 (58.15)	3.92 (3.94)	10.41 (10.43)
5j	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	60	172-173	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	58.12 (58.15)	3.92 (3.94)	10.40 (10.43)
5k	H	2-FC ₆ H ₄	62	255	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ FN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	59.96 (59.98)	4.02 (4.07)	10.74 (10.76)
5l	H	4-FC ₆ H ₄	60	262	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ FN ₄ O ₃ S ₂	60.19 (60.21)	4.19 (4.28)	10.76 (10.80)

rial activity was carried out against, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* and *S. pyogenus*. The standard drug used was Gentamycin and antifungal activity against *C. albicans*,

A. niger and *A. clavatus*. The standard antifungal Nystatin was used for a comparison of result and are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of compound **5b-1**

Compd.	Antimicrobial activity is expressed in the form of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)				Antifungal activity is expressed in the form of Minimal Fungicidal Concentration		
	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> MTCC	<i>S. aureus</i> MTCC	<i>S. pyogenus</i> MTCC	<i>C. albicans</i> MTCC	<i>A. niger</i> MTCC	<i>A. clavatus</i> MTCC
	443	1688	96	442	227	282	1323
5a	500	25	1000	50	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
5b	25	500	500	25	500	1000	> 1000
5c	1000	50	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
5d	1000	1000	1000	1000	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
5e	25	100	200	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
5f	500	500	250	250	1000	1000	> 1000
5g	500	500	500	500	> 1000	> 1000	1000
5h	12.5	500	50	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
5i	200	500	500	500	500	500	1000
5j	12.5	25	1000	1000	500	1000	> 1000
5k	500	500	500	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
5l	500	500	1000	1000	1000	> 1000	> 1000

Experimental

Melting point was taken in open capillaries and is uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr disk) were recorded on FT-IR-therminicolate IR 200 spectrometer and ^1H spectra on a Bruker DRX 300 in CDCl_3 at 200 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compound was checked by TLC on silica gel (350 mesh size) plate and the final compound is purified by column chromatography using silica gel (60–80 mesh size) column.

2-Thioxo-3-p-tolyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-quinazolin-4-one 1 : A mixture of carbon disulphide (0.03 mole) and *p*-toluidine (0.012 mole) was added dropwise to a refluxing mixture of anthranilic acid (0.010 mole) and potassium hydroxide (0.012 mole) in methanol (15 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux for 10 h, then poured over ice to get a solid product, dissolved in 10% potassium hydroxide solution and filtered. Conc. HCl was added to the filtrate. The white precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with cold methanol (50%). The product is recrystallized from methanol to get compound **1**. Yield 75%, m.p. 275 °C (Found : C, 67.10; H, 4.50; N, 10.42; O, 5.93. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 67.14; H, 4.51; N, 12.44; O, 5.96%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3130, 3070, 1340, 829 (aromatic ring), 1660 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$ cyclic), 3450, 3240, 1530 ($>\text{N}-\text{H}$ of sec. amine), 1270 ($>\text{C}=\text{S}$ str. thioamide); ^1H NMR : δ 13.01 (1H, s, exch.), 2.34 (3H, s), 6.70–7.3 (5H, m), 7.52 (2H, d), 7.8 (1H, d).

(4-Oxo-3-p-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazolin-2-yl-sulfanyl)-

acetic acid ethyl ester 2 : The equimolar solution of compound **1** (0.1 mole) and ethyl chloro acetate (0.1 mole) in dry acetone (35 ml), in presence of K_2CO_3 (0.15 mole) was refluxed on a water bath for about 40 h. The reaction mixture was poured in ice to get a solid product, washed with methanol (50%). The product is recrystallized from ethanol to get compound **2**. Yield 78%, m.p. 133 °C (Found : C, 64.37; H, 5.11; N, 7.88; O, 13.11. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 64.39; H, 5.12; N, 7.90; O, 13.54%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3060 (C–H str. aromatic), 2930 (C–H str.), 1785 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$ carbonyl), 1645 (C=O str.), 1665 (C=N str.), 1620 (C=C str. aromatic ring), 1390 (C–H bonding), 1270 (C–O–C str.), 1315 (C–N str. aromatic), 815 (C–H bending *p*-substituted), 790 (C–H str.); ^1H NMR : δ 1.3 (3H, t), 2.35 (3H, s), 4.12 (2H, q), 4.48 (2H, s), 6.9–7.5 (3H, m), 7.54 (2H, d), 7.9 (1H, d).

(4-Oxo-3-p-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazolin-2-yl-sulfanyl)-acetic acid hydrazide 3 : An equimolar mixture of compound **2** (0.1 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mole) were placed in a round bottom flask and then ethanol (40 ml) was added as a solvent. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h, followed by cooling at room temperature and the product is separated, filtered and washed with water, recrystallized from ethanol to get compound **3**. Yield 75%, m.p. 208 °C (Found : C, 59.95; H, 4.72; N, 16.43; O, 9.3. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 59.98; H, 4.74; N, 16.46; O, 9.4%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3450 ($>\text{NH}$

str.), 3270 (>NH str. secondary amide), 2910 (CH str. CH₂); ¹H NMR : δ 2.36 (3H, s), 4.40 (2H, s), 4.85 (2H, s), 6.9–7.6 (8H, m), 8.0 (1H, s).

(4-Oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazolin-2-yl-sulfanyl) acetic acid-(4-hydroxy benzylidene)-hydrazide **4a** : A mixture of compound **3** (0.01 mole) and *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde (0.01 mole) in ethanol was refluxed. During the reflux 2–3 drops of acetic acid was added and reflux continued for 8 h. After completion of reaction the product was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then recrystallized from methanol and chloroform (1 : 1 v/v) solution to get compound **4a**. Yield 70%, m.p. 245 °C (Found : C, 64.83; H, 4.52; N, 12.56; O, 10.87. Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₀N₄O₃S : C, 64.85; H, 4.54; N, 12.60; O, 10.80%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3520 (-OH str.), 3345 (-NH str. sec. >N-H), 3100 (-CH str. =CH-aromatic), 2910 (-CH str. -CH), 810 (*p*-substituted); ¹H NMR : δ 2.37 (3H, s), 4.45 (1H, s), 4.86 (2H, s), 5.2 (1H, s), 6.9–7.75 (12H, m), 8.15 (1H, s).

N-[2-(4-Hydroxy-phenyl)-4-oxo-thiazolidin-3-yl]-2-(4-oxo-3-*p*-tolyl-3,4-dihydro-quinazolin-2-yl-sulfanyl)-acetamide **5a** : A mixture of **4a** (0.01 mole) in ethanol or dioxan and mercapto acetic acid (0.01 mole) with a pinch of ZnCl₂ was refluxed on a heating mantle for about 10 h. The separated solid was crystallized from methanol to get a compound **5a**. Yield 70%, m.p. 241 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 609 (-CH str.), 3270 (>NH str. secondary amide), 1650 (>C=O ter. amide); ¹H NMR : δ 2.37 (3H, s), 3.6 (2H, s), 4.48 (2H, s), 5.2 (1H, s), 7.0–7.95 (12H, m), 8.55 (1H, s).

Other compounds **5b-n** was synthesized similarly from **4b-n** respectively. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

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